

The Lesser of Two Evils? Sexual Homicide as an “Hybrid” Offense

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Introduction

Sexual homicide combines the act of murder with acts of a sexual nature, often as a form of rape or other sexual assault. Rape and murder are considered to be “evil”, and when combined, sexual homicide is the most serious crime that can be committed (DeLisi, 2001; Sellin & Wolfgang, 1964; Warr, 1989). Although sexual homicide is relatively infrequent, studies have shown that the most serious crimes are perpetrated by around 5% of the criminal population (e.g., Loeber, Farrington, Stouthamer-Loeber, Moffitt, & Caspi, 1998; Arnold & Kay, 1999; Farrington & West, 1993). Data from the FBI show that a murder is committed every 35.6 minutes and a rape every 6.2 minutes (DeLisi, 2015). Moreover, these crimes are associated with enormous costs for society in general and the criminal justice system in particular. As an illustration, DeLisi, Kosloski, Sween, Hachmeister, Moore, and Drury (2010) estimated the cost of a sexual homicide to approximately \$20 million per incident. Yet, mainstream criminology has been reluctant to consider the study of sexual homicide as a legitimate research area. As mentioned by DeLisi and Wright (2014), a direct consequence of this failure to research sexual homicide is that criminological theories are often performing poorly to explain the most pathological forms of criminal violence and the offenders committing it. One of the reasons cited to explain this academic neglect is a simple lack of opportunity. As demonstrated by DeLisi (2001), even some of the most important and frequently used datasets available in criminology had low numbers of rape and murder, let alone sexual homicide. Thus, this led criminology to focus on the most common and normative offenders instead of the most violent criminals and those who are responsible for the most damage and costs to society. Even so, there is still another reason for criminology overlooking the study of sexual homicide. It has been suggested that mainstream criminology has often considered sexual homicide and its offenders as too

sensationalistic, a type of crime mainly associated with popular culture and not worthy of scientific empirical investigation (DeLisi & Wright, 2014).

Fortunately for criminology, some journals such as the *Journal of Criminal Justice* have found it important to not only consider the more mundane delinquency, but to allocate a disproportionate focus on papers addressing the more severe and pathological offenders and their crimes (DeLisi, 2015). This focus on the most extreme forms of violence is beneficial as this may inspire innovation and new approaches to old questions. Moreover, such initiative often sparks ideas as to how to test criminological concepts within this specific criminal population (e.g., James, Beauregard, & Proulx, 2019). Furthermore, this may push the field of criminology to sharpen their theories and integrate some of the most important factors contributing to the explanation of serious interpersonal violence (DeLisi, Conis, & Beaver, 2012). This is something that can now be done as more rigorous quantitative methods are available to the study of sexual homicide given the existence of larger databases (DeLisi, 2015). For instance, when we published our first ever empirical paper in 2002, we had access to a sample of 36 sexual murderers (see Beauregard & Proulx, 2002). As a comparison, some of our most recent studies on sexual homicide were based on a sample of 762 cases (e.g., Chopin & Beauregard, 2019).

This vision has led to the creation of this special issue on *Criminology and Criminal Extremity: New Development for Sexual Homicide*. As an introduction to this special issue, we wanted to raise two different but complementary issues that may have also contributed to neglecting the study of sexual homicide specifically by mainstream criminology. First, we are discussing the evolution of knowledge on the sexual murderer and his offense and how it now appears that these offenders should be considered as a specific type of offender – not as a murderer nor as just a sex offender. Second, we conceptualize sexual homicide as a hybrid

offense – one that combines murder and sexual assault – and argue that criminology has once again failed to examine complex crimes that combine two specific types of crimes (e.g., sexual burglary). By doing so, we are hoping to provide additional understanding of the crime of sexual homicide, as well as highlighting the need for more research by criminology on extreme and complex forms of crimes.

Sexual Homicide and Sexual Murderer: A Specific Type of Crime by a Specific Type of Offender

Although the field of criminology has been late to the study of sexual homicide, these crimes have been the object of some research, largely dominated by the field of psychology and psychiatry. A first generation of studies presented case descriptions of individuals who had killed their victim during a sexual assault. For instance, Krafft-Ebing (1886) presented a comprehensive collection of case studies to gain insight into the phenomenon of lust murder. Although similar descriptive and case studies followed, they all assumed that individuals committing a sexual homicide should be considered a distinct type of offender. Brittain (1970) offered a psychosocial profile of individuals who had killed their victims following a sexual assault. His analysis described individuals presenting a narcissistic and egocentric personality with some obsessive traits, which were typically reflected at the crime scene. They often felt different from others and were likely to remain single. These individuals also tended to present more than one paraphilia (e.g., cross-dressing, fetishism, masochism) as well as cruelty against animals. The killing – which was planned and against a victim who was chosen randomly or for reasons unknown to others – usually happened following a threat to his self-esteem. Although informative, Brittain's (1970) study was mainly based on his clinical experience and no information was provided regarding the number of cases he had encountered to come up with this portrait.

To overcome some of the issues with the case studies approach, an extensive study was undertaken by the FBI Behavioral Science Unit, in large part through the work of Ressler and his colleagues (e.g., Burgess, Hartman, Ressler, Douglas, & McCormack, 1986; Ressler, Burgess, & Douglas, 1988). These researchers interviewed 36 individuals who had been convicted of a total of 118 sexual homicides to learn about modus operandi, crime scene characteristics, and methods employed to escape detection. Based on these 36 cases, they proposed a typology with two main profiles: organized and disorganized. The *organized* offender is intelligent and socially and sexually competent. This offender is more likely to show a controlled mood during crime, to use alcohol, and to live with a partner. The organized offender is mobile, possessing a car in good condition, follows the crime in news media, and may change jobs or leave town after the murder. His crime is planned, he is likely to target a stranger, and the crime scene reflects an offender who has control over their offense. This offender uses restraints, will exhibit aggressive acts prior to death, and may transport and hide the victim's body after the murder. Usually the weapon or evidence will be absent from the crime scene. As to the *disorganized* offender, he is of average intelligence, socially immature, presents a poor work history, and is sexually incompetent. This offender shows an anxious mood during the crime, is not likely to use alcohol, lives alone, and usually lives and/or works near the crime scene. He has minimal interest in news media coverage of his crime and is not likely to change his lifestyle. The crime of the disorganized offender is usually spontaneous, on a known victim, and the crime scene is random and sloppy. He is not likely to use restraints, but sexual acts are committed after death. The body is normally left in view, at the death scene, and the murder weapon and evidence are often present.

The FBI study along with other descriptive studies (e.g., Brown, 1991) enabled the identification of several characteristics that appeared to be associated with sexual homicide. However, concerns were raised about the validity of these findings as previous studies did not include control groups. Thus, it was impossible to know whether these characteristics identified were truly associated to a specific type of offender or if it was in fact common to most individuals committing sexual assaults.

To better understand the potential differences between individuals who commit sexual homicides and those who commit nonlethal sexual assaults, a second generation of studies focused on comparing the two groups. Early attempts examined the sociodemographic/developmental, psychological, and pre-crime factors (e.g., Grubin, 1994; Langevin et al., 1988; Milsom et al., 2001) and showed that sexual homicides were more likely to be committed by older offenders, socially isolated, who reported more runaways as a child, and with less prior convictions for sexual crimes. Moreover, these individuals showed more overcontrolled anger, voyeurism, transvestism, and sadism compared to individuals who did not kill their victims during a sexual assault. Finally, these studies showed that sexual homicides were more likely to be committed by individuals who were socially isolated prior to the crime, lived alone, had no sexual partner, and almost no sexual experience. These findings were interesting but the studies suffered from several limitations, such as the use of small – sometimes even biased – samples and more importantly, a limited number of variables examined.

Proulx, Beauregard, Cusson, and Nicole (2007) attempted to remedy this situation by examining an extensive list of factors using a representative sample including 40 sexual murderers and 101 rapists. Among the hundreds of variables investigated, their findings showed that sexual murderers were more likely to report being victim of incest, disciplinary problems in

school, social isolation, and deviant sexual fantasies in childhood. Although no significant differences were observed between the two groups as to personality, the study showed that sexual murderers were more likely to exhibit anger prior to crime, as well as a greater use of alcohol and weapons. More recently, a systematic review by Stefanska, Beech, and Carter (2016) examined ten published studies comparing the same two groups of offenders. The findings revealed that sexual murderers were less likely to have committed vaginal penetration, to plan the crime (Higgs et al., 2015; Salfati & Taylor, 2006; Vettor & Beech, 2014), and to humiliate the victim (Healey, Lussier, & Beauregard, 2013; Higgs et al., 2015). Moreover, the findings were inconclusive as to whether the victim was restrained as well as if they differed in physical victimization, relationship status at the time of the crime, low self-esteem, and age at the time of crime (Stefanska et al., 2016).

Despite some differences observed between the two groups of offenders, overall, the conclusions of these studies were that sexual murderers and rapists presented more similarities than differences. It was suggested that offenders should not be distinguished based on the outcome of the crime (i.e., lethal or not) and therefore, sexual murderers did not represent a distinct type of offender. A thorough review of the findings of various studies from the second generation led to the realization that they did not reflect our experience with these offenders. While the idea of comparing sexual homicide to rape furthered our understanding of the sexual murderer, something particularly important was overlooked. It was assumed that we could compare sexual homicides to sexual assaults that included both violent and non-violent sexual assaults. The inclusion of both violent and non-violent sexual assaults in the same group may have introduced some noise in previous findings. To shed some light on possible differences that

may have been missed between these two types of offenders, a third generation of studies compared sexual homicide cases to cases of both violent and non-violent sexual assaults.

Beauregard and Martineau (2016) examined differences among these three types of sexual assaults on several characteristics. Among the factors investigated, they have looked specifically at the differences related to paraphilias. Perpetrators of sexual homicide significantly differed in terms of paraphilic behaviors. These offenders were significantly more likely to have engaged in paraphilic behavior both as a juvenile and as an adult. Although individuals who have perpetrated sexual homicides were significantly more likely to have engaged in a lifetime of paraphilic behavior, they were significantly less likely than the two other groups who had committed violent and non-violent sexual assaults to be involved in paraphilias involving nonconsenting adults and children. Interestingly, it was the individuals who engaged in non-violent sexual assaults that were the most likely to engage in pedophilia, whereas individuals who had committed violent sexual assaults were most likely to engage in rape.

Beauregard and Martineau (2016) also examined developmental factors among the three types of sexual crimes. Offenders who have committed a non-violent sexual assault were more likely to report having been victim of sexual contact during childhood. As for individuals who committed violent sexual assaults, these offenders were more likely to report having been victim of parental abandonment, were younger when they had their first sexual intercourse, and they were more likely to come from families with prior suicide attempts/completion as well as families with prior convictions for sexual crimes. As to the individuals involved in sexual homicides, they were characterized by many problems in their childhood, such as victim of physical violence, incest, social isolation, chronic lying, prostitution, poor self-image, cruelty against animals, and an angry temperament.

Sexual murderers present a background characterized by abuse and a variety of problematic behaviors. These findings suggested that offenders committing sexual homicides learn specific sexual behaviors early in childhood that suggest a strong need for sexual gratification, and they also may not adequately address their sexual needs, which potentially contributes to the seriousness of their sexual offending. Beauregard and DeLisi (2018a) hypothesized that this investment in solitary, illegal or obsessive sexual behaviors is the result of their need to regain some control over their lives, as suggested by several of the theoretical models of sexual homicide.

Beauregard and DeLisi (2018b) further investigated the issue of personality in perpetrators of sexual homicide by comparing the same three groups. Using multivariate analyses and controlling for other factors that have been associated to the commission of sexual homicide, they found that the personality profile of the perpetrators of sexual homicide is comprised primarily of Schizoid and Borderline Personality Disorders. These offenders were also significantly more likely to select a victim, use a weapon, and use drugs and alcohol before their offenses, but less likely to force their victim to engage in sexual acts or humiliate them. Beauregard and DeLisi (2018b) argued that the comorbidity of Schizoid, Borderline, and Antisocial Personality Disorder features presented unique personality dysfunction that facilitates the lethal sexual violence relative to the non-lethal sexual violence.

Beauregard, DeLisi, and Hewitt (2017) examined differences among the three groups of offenders on their criminal career. Even though all three groups had extensive and serious offending records, some important distinctions were found. Individuals who had committed sexual assaults without expressive violence had more convictions for rape/sexual abuse and other sexual offenses relating to exhibitionism as well as more specialization in their offending repertoires.

Individuals who had committed violent sexual assaults were more versatile in their offending patterns and had more assaults, homicides, kidnappings, and aggravated sexual assaults. Offenders who have committed sexual homicides were similarly versatile and had extensive histories of armed robbery, kidnapping, and homicide.

Chopin and Beauregard (2019) have taken a similar approach to answer the same question but this time including a group of individuals who had committed non-sexual homicides. Comparing a large sample of individuals who have committed sexual homicides, violent sexual assaults, and non-sexual homicides, they found that perpetrators of sexual homicide presented several differences that were consistent with the other two groups. These convergent differences suggested that offenders who perpetrated a sexual homicide were different not only from perpetrators of sexual crimes but also from individuals who had committed a non-sexual homicide. Even more interesting was the fact that these differences were not only identified as to the crime characteristics but on the offender characteristics as well. Overall, these findings are suggesting that when offenders combine the act of murder with a sexual assault, it results in a very distinct type of crime – one criminology has long overlooked.

Complexity of Hybrid Offenses

In addition to being a distinct crime, sexual homicide can also be described as a “hybrid” offense. We are not referring to the common law definition where hybrid offenses are those that can be prosecuted either summarily or as indictment. Instead, we refer to a more literal definition of the term, meaning something that has been produced by the combination of two or more distinct elements. By combining the act of murder and sexual assault, sexual homicide has been overlooked – not only by criminologists (even by those specialized in homicide) but also by the field of research on sexual violence. We argue that the complexity associated with the

combination of two distinct types of crime into a new one, could represent another reason as to why these hybrid offenses are under-researched. The case of sexual burglary is a good example.

Contrary to sexual homicide, the crime of burglary is not uncommon. However, similarly to sexual homicide, the research on sexual burglary has been very limited and the estimation of its true prevalence is hampered by the usual limitations associated with official statistics or offenses being pled down (Harris et al., 2013). Nonetheless, Harris et al. (2013) pointed out that across several studies on sex offenders, between 22 and 50 percent of these offenders presented a history of burglary (e.g., Harris, Pedneault, & Knight, 2009; Soothill et al., 2000) and between one third and one half of all rapes are committed in the victim's residence (see Amir, 1971, Warr, 1988).

It has been suggested that the crime of burglary could represent an important “stepping stone” to the development of a sexual criminal career (DeLisi & Scherer, 2006; Schlesinger & Revitch, 1999; Vaughn, DeLisi, Beaver, & Howard, 2008). According to DeLisi and Walters (2011), “to the modal criminal offender, burglary is the pathway to access property; to others, it is the gateway to the goals of kidnapping, rape, and murder.” (p. 151). Sex offenders who present a history of burglary have been found to have an early onset of their offending, more charges, and with a longer criminal career (Harris et al., 2013). Despite this apparent connection, the link between burglary and sexual assault is far from obvious. Thus, burglary is a property offense most often committed in the absence of the occupants and motivated by material gain, while a sexual assault is a crime against the person that requires contact with the victim (Harris, et al., 2013). As to sexual burglary, explanations fall into three categories (Pedneault, Beauregard, Harris, & Knight, 2015): (a) the burglary was the main goal of the offender and the sexual assault was just a “bonus” to the theft, when the offender unexpectedly found himself in a

situation with a suitable victim, in a home he thought unoccupied (i.e., an opportunistic rape); (b) the sexual assault was the main goal of the offence and the theft was the bonus to the sexual offence (Scully & Marolla, 1985); and (c) the situational cues that make a location appealing for a burglary also make that same location appealing for a violent offence and the sexual assault is not accidental (Warr, 1988). Recent studies do not support the idea that burglary occurs as a bonus to a sexual assault since targets often feature characteristics that would be deemed counter-indicative for a monetary-based burglary (Pedneault et al., 2015).

In fact, studies suggest that sexual burglary represents – similar to sexual homicide – a specific type of crime, different from other forms of burglaries. For instance, Vaughn et al. (2008) identified a typology of career criminals who committed burglary. Among the four categories identified, the *sexual predator burglar* was one type representing only 6% of the cases but were “disproportionately involved in the most serious forms and total incidence of crime” (Vaughn et al., 2008, p. 1390). These burglars were also the most violent (i.e., aggravated assault and robbery), had the longest criminal careers (i.e., over 30 years, earliest age of onset), and had a history of sexual deviance (e.g., rape and prostitution/solicitation offenses). Similar to what we mentioned earlier, Vaughn et al. (2008) suggested that the burglary of the sexual predator could represent an indicator for even more serious homicide offending.

Moreover, some studies suggested that even by focusing on sexual burglary itself, various types existed, similar to the heterogeneity observed in sexual homicide (Beauregard & Proulx, 2002). For instance, Schlesinger and Revitch (1999) were the first to propose that sexual burglars could be classified into overt sexual burglars (i.e., those involved in direct sexual contacts) or covert sexual burglars (i.e., those involved in voyeuristic acts). Following this, Pedneault, Harris, and Knight (2012) identified three types of sexual burglary. The *fetishistic noncontact burglaries*

are those that are committed in unoccupied houses and involve fetishistic behavior (e.g., accessing female clothing that has erotic value to the offender), without any theft, violence, or the use of a weapon. As to the *versatile contact burglaries*, they consist of rape committed in the victim residence (i.e., an apartment), involving theft, as well as the use of violence and a weapon. Finally, *sexually oriented contact burglaries* are incidents of rape also committed in the victim residence (i.e., house) without theft, violence, or the use of a weapon.

As can be seen, whether it is sexual burglary or sexual homicide, both should be seen as hybrid offense – combining two different forms of crime. In sexual homicide, the offender combines the acts of murder and sexual assault. It seems that the combination of two forms of crime has pushed the field to maybe consider the lesser of two evils. On one hand, due to the sexual nature of the crime, the field of criminology has neglected to examine these cases, assuming that the field of sexual violence – often dominated by psychology and psychiatry – would be better suited to study this type of crime (Lussier & Beauregard, 2015). On the other hand, the field of research on sexual violence has also been reluctant to pay attention to sexual homicide, mainly due to the act of murder that dominated these crimes. We argue that crimes such as sexual homicide represent a specific and hybrid offense that cannot be “dismembered” from its constitutional parts. We should not have to ask again whether sexual homicide should be considered more as a murder or a sexual crime; there is “no lesser of two evils.” It is ipso factor its own crime combining two of the most damaging criminal acts to form one distinct offense.

The Special Issue

The research on sexual homicide has made giant steps during the past 20 years. Researchers involved in the study of this crime have answered several crucial questions. However, as it is often the case in research, more questions have surfaced. This special issue

entitled *Criminology and Criminal Extremity: New Development for Sexual Homicide* assembles a collection of articles published by leading scholars in the field, pushing back the borders of knowledge on this extreme form of violence. Largely guided by theoretical and applied criminology, these studies examine strategies used by sexual murderers to avoid detection, group offending, sadism, specific populations, and whether sexual homicide is the result of an escalation or just a different intent. Moreover, the studies included in the special issue suggest tools that may be of use in the criminal justice system to potentially identify cases of sexual homicide, as well as how the various level of violence may be used to better understand these offenders. We are grateful to the Editor-in-Chief of *Journal of Criminal Justice*, Matt DeLisi, for this opportunity to have a whole special issue devoted to sexual homicide. With this special issue we are hoping to spark some interest in criminologists for the study of extreme – albeit rare – forms of violence such as sexual homicide, as well as a closer look at these hybrid offenses. The field of criminology can only benefit from more studies of their criminal evil.

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